

RawAlign: Accurate, Fast, and Scalable Raw Nanopore Signal Mapping via Combining Seeding and Alignment

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Nanopore sequencers generate raw electrical signals representing the contents of a biological sequence molecule passing through the nanopore. These signals can be analyzed directly, avoiding basecalling entirely. We observe that while existing proposals for raw signal analysis typically do well in all metrics for small genomes (e.g., viral genomes), they all perform poorly for large genomes (e.g., the human genome). **Our goal** is to analyze raw nanopore signals in an accurate, fast, and scalable manner. To this end, we propose *RawAlign*, the first work to integrate fine-grained signal alignment into the state-of-the-art raw signal mapper. To enable accurate, fast, and scalable mapping with alignment, *RawAlign* implements three algorithmic improvements and hardware acceleration via a vectorized implementation of fine-grained alignment. Together, these significantly reduce the overhead of typically computationally expensive fine-grained alignment. Our extensive evaluations on different use cases and various datasets show *RawAlign* provides 1) the most accurate mapping for large genomes and 2) and on-par performance compared to *RawHash* (between $0.80\times$ - $1.08\times$), while achieving better performance than *UNCALLED* and *Sigmap* by on average (geo. mean) $2.83\times$ and $2.06\times$, respectively. **Availability:** <https://github.com/CMU-SAFARI/RawAlign>

1. Introduction

Nanopore-based sequencers generate a series of raw electrical signal measurements representing the contents of a biological sequence molecule passing through the sequencer’s nanopore. Nanopore sequencers provide unique features and, thus, pose unique challenges to computational analysis [1–4]. For example, sequencers can provide real-time control over the sequencing of individual molecules with a mechanism called *Read Until* [5]. *Read Until* ejects a molecule from its pore before it is fully sequenced if deemed irrelevant (e.g., by computational methods) [6]. The challenge to efficiently leveraging such real-time control is to (1) make *timely* decisions (otherwise, sequencing time is wasted), (2) make *accurate* decisions (otherwise, relevant data may be lost, or data may be

biased), (3) match at least the *throughput* of the sequencer (otherwise, the computation is not real-time) [7–9].

Although a common approach for real-time analysis starts with translating raw nanopore signals into nucleotide characters with the *basecalling* step, a number of recent works enable analyzing raw nanopore signals directly without basecalling [10, 11] to enable a faster and power-efficient analysis (e.g., [7–9, 12–21]). Such an analysis can mainly be useful for better scalability and portable sequencing in resource-constrained devices [7]. These earlier works already enable important applications such as relative abundance calculation, contamination testing, and real-time sequencing decisions while completely forgoing the need for basecalling (i.e., converting the raw signals to the nucleotide bases A, C, G, and T). Among these works, the state-of-the-art work [8, 9] enables mapping these raw nanopore signals to a reference genome using a quick hash-based search followed by chaining. Such a coarse-grained sequence comparison is fast and scales well to large reference genomes, but (1) has relatively low accuracy, and (2) lacks fine-grained sequence alignments in the output, limiting its applicability to downstream analysis tasks (e.g., variant calling).

Our goal is to analyze raw nanopore signals in an accurate, fast, and scalable manner. To this end, we propose *RawAlign*, the first tool to combine fast and scalable hash-based raw signal mapping algorithms with highly accurate alignment based on dynamic time warping (DTW) [22–24] to enable better accuracy and performance, while allowing future work to focus on further downstream analysis after mapping using the fine-grained alignment information (e.g., variant calling).

However, combining DTW with a hash-based raw signal mapper to enable scalable and accurate analysis is not trivial as we identify three key **challenges**. First, DTW is a computationally costly algorithm that prevents the earlier works that use DTW from scaling to perform real-time analysis for larger genomes [7, 14, 15]. Second, hash-based raw signal mappers tend to generate many candidate regions based on hash matches, resulting in fre-

quent calls to the DTW subroutine, exacerbating DTW’s already high computational cost. Third, DTW’s scoring mechanism is not directly suitable for integration with the mapping decision process because it depends on variables such as path length and cumulative distance, which may not accurately reflect the optimal alignment or the best mapping quality in the context of raw signal data.

To tackle these challenges, RawAlign efficiently integrates DTW into a hash-based raw signal mapper by designing and integrating optimizations when calculating DTW and improving the decision-making process in four directions:

- The number of candidate locations is reduced with RawHash’s chaining-based filtering (see §2.1)
- The number of calls to the DTW subroutine is further reduced via an early termination strategy (see §2.4.1)
- The number of arithmetic operations for the DTW computation is reduced via *anchor-guided alignment* (see §2.4.2) and *banding/windowing* (see §2.4.3)
- The arithmetic operations are implemented efficiently through Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD) [25] vectorization (see §2.4.4)

In combination, this strategy makes DTW efficient and scalable to large genomes, enabling RawAlign to analyze raw nanopore signals efficiently and accurately for a wide range of reference genome sizes.

We make the following contributions:

- We develop RawAlign, the first tool for raw signal mapping to combine seeding and alignment.
- We comprehensively evaluate RawAlign and demonstrate its applicability to a wide range of datasets. RawAlign provides similar throughput to RawHash while consistently improving accuracy.
- We develop optimization techniques that collectively make practical the combination of seeding and alignment for raw nanopore signal analysis.
- We demonstrate that RawAlign is the first tool to map raw nanopore signals to large reference genomes with high accuracy.
- We demonstrate the generality of RawAlign by integrating it with and comprehensively comparing it to RawHash2.
- We open-source all code of RawAlign and associated evaluation methodology, available at <https://github.com/CMU-SAFARI/RawAlign>. RawAlign can be readily used as a raw nanopore signal mapper.

2. Methods

To identify the mapping positions and the alignment between a reference genome and a raw nanopore signal, RawAlign works in three major steps: (1) offline reference database pre-processing (see Sup.§A.1), (2) online read pre-processing (see Sup.§A.2), and (3) online mapping of the reads with the Seed-Filter-Align paradigm (see §2.1). Fig. 1 shows the overview of the steps that RawAlign takes to perform the mapping. RawAlign uses the seeding and filtering methods from the prior work RawHash [8]. We explain the alignment based on dynamic time warping (DTW) in detail in §2.2, and we explain how RawAlign uses the result from DTW for making mapping decisions in §2.3. To make the Seed-Filter-Align paradigm practical for raw signal mapping, we introduce four strategies to improve the performance of the alignment step in §2.4.

Figure 1: Overview of RawAlign.

2.1. Mapping via Seed-Filter-Align

RawAlign follows the *Seed-Filter-Align* or *Seed-Filter-Extend* paradigm, which has been applied with great success by conventional basecalled read mappers (e.g., [26–28]). The main mapping process consists of three steps: *seeding*, *filtering*, and *alignment*. Fig. 2 shows a real example of each of these steps in RawAlign for a read in the d2 *E. Coli* dataset.

2.1.1. Seeding. First, during seeding, RawAlign finds a large number of possible candidate locations via fuzzy matches between the read and the reference database (Fig. 2, left). Seeding is relatively fast and scales well to large reference genomes. To find these seed matches, RawAlign uses the seeding step of RawHash [8], which

works in three steps as shown in Fig. 1. First, it converts both the reference genome and raw nanopore signals into a discrete set of signals representing k-mers, called *events*. Second, to reduce the residual noise in these events (*i.e.*, due to certain imperfections in sequencing and raw signal-to-discrete signal conversion), RawHash quantizes these events and generates hash values from these quantized values, called *seeds*. Third, the locations where each seed occurs in the reference database are obtained by querying the index with the seed. The read-reference location pairs are called *anchors*.

Figure 2: Example of RawAlign’s Usage of Seed-Filter-Align.

2.1.2. Filtering. Second, during filtering, RawAlign reduces the number of anchors by heuristically evaluating and removing those that do not look promising. Filtering is a relatively coarse-granular comparison between sequences, and hence, faster than DTW-based alignment but less accurate on its own. One class of filters is *chaining* (as we show in the middle plot in Fig. 2 and in Fig. 1). During chaining, the relative positions of anchors are evaluated with a dynamic programming algorithm to identify a set of anchors that is approximately colinear in the read and reference sequence. RawAlign uses the same chaining logic as RawHash [8] and Sigmap [12].

2.1.3. Alignment. Third, during *alignment* or *extension*, RawAlign re-evaluates all remaining candidate regions after chaining (see Fig. 1) at fine granularity using dynamic time warping (DTW) (Fig. 2, right). This finely granular comparison significantly improves accuracy relative to prior works that avoid it (*e.g.*, [8, 9]). We elaborate in §2.2 why DTW [7, 14, 15, 22–24] is a natural choice to evaluate candidate locations, what its challenges are, and how RawAlign overcomes them.

2.2. Alignment via Dynamic Time Warping

To perform a pairwise comparison and alignment of *basecalled* sequences, *Needleman-Wunsch* (NW) is a widely used algorithm [29]. However, these commonly used algorithms for basecalled sequences are *not* suitable for aligning signals as the length of the signals can vary

due to the varying speed at which biological molecules move through the nanopore during sequencing, known as *translocation speed*. Variations in translocation speed result in time distortions in the signal data. This makes raw signal analysis a time-series analysis to handle this time variance.

Dynamic time warping (DTW) is an algorithm for fine-grained pairwise comparison and alignment of time series data [22–24], such as two raw nanopore signals. Multiple prior works use DTW to compare raw nanopore signals to entire reference genomes (*e.g.*, SquiggleFilter [7], DT-Wax [15], and HARU [14]). To show how DTW can handle the time variance in signals compared to NW while identifying similarities between a pair of signals (as in NW), we show the differences and similarities between NW and DTW in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Conceptual Similarity of Needleman-Wunsch and Dynamic Time Warping.

The key similarity between NW and DTW is that both are based on dynamic programming, filling a two-dimensional table of numbers. Each entry in the dynamic programming table is computed based on three neighbor entries in the north, northwest, and west according to simple update rules. The final alignment score (for NW) or cost (for DTW) is the entry in the southwest corner of the table.

There are two key differences between NW and DTW: First, NW’s update rule performs exact character comparisons, suitable for aligning basecalled sequences where nucleotides either match or do not match (*e.g.*, $A=A$, $A \neq G$). In contrast, DTW computes the numerical difference between signal values, which accommodates the continuous and noisy nature of raw signal data (*e.g.*, $0.2 \approx 0.3$, but $0.1 \neq 0.9$). Second, NW imposes fixed penalties for insertions and deletions (*indels*), independent of the sequence content, which is appropriate for sequences with rare indels. DTW, however, adjusts penalties based on the similarity of the signal values, effectively handling frequent indels caused by variable translocation rates and segmentation imperfections in raw nanopore signals (see Sup.§A.2).

2.3. Alignment Score and Mapping Decisions

RawAlign bases its mapping decisions (Continue Mapping part in Fig. 1) mainly on the alignment (DTW) cost (see §2.2). The DTW cost is always positive, where a low cost indicates a good match between the read and the reference, thus low-cost candidate regions should generally be preferred. However, the DTW cost monotonically increases with sequence length, meaning that a long, well-matching candidate region typically has a higher DTW cost than a short, well-matching candidate region. That is undesirable because a long, well-matching region intuitively should be preferred over a short one, as they indicate a better match between the read and the reference.

To address this issue, RawAlign employs a customized alignment scoring scheme based on the DTW cost C_{DTW} and a constant *match bonus* B_{Match} that is scaled by the number of aligned read events N_{Read} :

$$Score = B_{Match} \times N_{Read} - C_{DTW}$$

With this scoring scheme, longer well-matching candidate regions achieve higher scores than shorter ones, provided B_{Match} is chosen appropriately. B_{Match} should be chosen such that it is above the noise floor of the sequencer, *i.e.*, such that two correctly aligned events usually differ by less than B_{Match} , or can be chosen using a parameter sweep.

Based on the alignment score, RawAlign considers the highest scoring candidate location as mapped if its score is at least above some threshold $Score_{Threshold}$. $Score_{Threshold}$ is necessary to avoid false positives in the presence of the match bonus; thus, the two parameters need to be chosen in conjunction.

2.4. Performance Optimizations to DTW

We observe, like prior work (*e.g.*, [7, 14, 15]), that DTW can have a high computational overhead if not applied judiciously. Prior works partially solve this challenge by proposing hardware accelerators for DTW [7, 14, 15]. RawAlign is, in principle, compatible with such accelerators and can benefit from them. However, to make it as out-of-the-box usable as possible, we optimize the DTW in RawAlign at both the algorithm and software level. Since RawAlign’s mapping decisions require only the alignment score but not the exact alignment path, the exact path is not computed by default but can be added to the output file via a command line flag. We optimize our DTW implementation via a combination of four techniques: (1) Early termination, (2) anchor-guided alignment, (3) banded alignment, and (4) SIMD.

2.4.1. Early Termination. Like other raw signal mappers, RawAlign outputs at most one mapping location per read. We observe that this can be exploited to terminate DTW early using a branch-and-bound approach, where we prune computations that cannot yield better results than the current best solution. We can safely terminate the DTW computation for a candidate location as we can prematurely confirm if a candidate location’s alignment score can surpass the current best alignment. This technique is most powerful if, by chance, the best candidate location with a very high alignment score is analyzed early, meaning all further alignments can be terminated more aggressively. To maximize the likelihood of the best candidate location being analyzed early, RawAlign sorts candidate locations by their chaining score before alignment.

2.4.2. Anchor-Guided Alignment. We observe that the optimal alignment of a chain typically includes the anchors in the chain. Thus, it is sufficient to align only the gaps between anchors and then combine the individual alignments or scores. This improves the performance because we can avoid performing unnecessary alignment operations for signals that a single anchor covers (usually from tens of signals up to a few hundred signals). Fig. 4 shows such an alignment path (*i.e.*, the diagonal path) between two anchors. Upper left and lower right cells in the dynamic programming matrix are anchors spanning a certain amount of signals. The alignment operations are performed without using the signals covered by these two cells in the matrix. Similar techniques have been applied by conventional basecalled read mappers (*e.g.*, minimap2 [26]) and can significantly reduce the number of dynamic programming cells that need to be computed. There can be a risk of inaccurate alignments if some of the anchors are not part of the globally optimal alignment; hence, RawAlign provides command line options for either anchor-guided or global (*i.e.*, non-anchor-guided) alignment. We observe that the accuracy loss due to anchor-guided alignment is typically small (< 1% F-1 score on all evaluated datasets). Thus, RawAlign uses anchor-guided alignment by default.

2.4.3. Banded Alignment. We observe that the optimal alignment of a chain or the gap between two anchors typically follows approximately the main diagonal (see Fig. 2 for an example and the diagonal path in Fig. 4). This can be exploited by only computing a subset of the DTW dynamic programming table, called a *band*. Fig. 4 shows the subset of an example of such a dynamic program-

Figure 4: Anchor-Guided Alignment and Banded Alignment.

ming table where the alignment is performed only by using the cells that fall under or overlap with two bands. The distance of these bands to the main diagonal band is known as *band width*. Similar techniques have been applied by conventional basecalled read mappers and basecalled sequence aligners (e.g., Edlib [30], KSW2 [31], minimap2 [26]). Banding can significantly reduce the number of arithmetic operations and memory accesses.

We observe that the read and reference sections of candidate pairs are rarely of the same length. Therefore, our banding implementation adjusts the band to follow a diagonal with a slope of $\frac{\text{read_segment_length}}{\text{reference_segment_length}}$ instead of the standard slope of 1, accommodating differences in sequence lengths between the read and reference segments.

2.4.4. SIMD. DTW is a standard two-dimensional dynamic programming algorithm that can be accelerated with techniques such as SIMD, GPUs [15], FPGAs [14], or ASICs [7].

We implement our banded dynamic time warping algorithm in an antidiagonal-wise [32] fashion, processing the dynamic programming matrix along its antidiagonals to enable efficient parallel computation. We further optimize the code to ensure that GCC v11.3.0 can auto-vectorize the critical innermost loop of the dynamic programming computation, which we verify via compilation logs.

3. Results

3.1. Evaluation Methodology

3.1.1. Baselines. We demonstrate the benefits of RawAlign by comparing to four prior works: UNCALLED [13], Sigmap [12], RawHash [8], and

RawHash2 [9]. We demonstrate the generality of RawAlign by integrating its alignment components into RawHash2 without specific tuning. We refer to this configuration as *RawAlign-RH2*. RawAlign and all four baselines are CPU-based. They accept a set of raw signal reads (e.g., FAST5 files) and a reference database (e.g., a FASTA file) to map to and produce mapping locations as a Pairwise mApping Format (PAF) file [33]. Due to a lack of a true ground truth in the read mapping experiments, we consider the mapping locations generated by minimap2 [26] as the ground truth and hence do not compare to its accuracy. In the relative abundance estimation evaluation, the true ground truth is known since the read set is artificially composed of reads from multiple species; thus, we compare the accuracy of the estimates to both minimap2 and the raw signal baselines.

3.1.2. Metrics. We evaluate each tool using five categories of metrics:

- **Memory footprint** (GB) during mapping as reported by Ubuntu’s time package; lower is better. We also report the indexing memory footprint in [Sup.Tab. S1](#).
- The mean **throughput** (bp/s) per mapping thread is crucial for real-time analysis. It should match or exceed the data generation rate of a nanopore sequencer, which is approximately 450 bp/s in recent Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) sequencers. Achieving this ensures that the computational analysis can keep up with the sequencing process; therefore, higher throughput is better. We also report the median throughput in [Sup.Tab. S1](#).
- Mean **analysis latency** (ms), *i.e.*, the time spent computing for mapping reads as reported by each tool in its PAF output; lower is better. We also report the median analysis latency in [Sup.Tab. S1](#).
- Mean **sequencing latency** (chunks), where one *chunk* corresponds to a segment of 450 base pairs—the typical data output per second from recent ONT sequencers. Sequencing latency represents the number of these chunks required to reach a mapping decision for each read, as reported by each tool in its PAF output; lower is better. UNCALLED reports the number of bases instead of the number of chunks, which we convert to the number of chunks by dividing by 450. Where available, we report the sequencing latency as the number of bases in [Sup.Tab. S1](#).
- **Accuracy** (F-1 score) based on the annotations from UNCALLED’s pafstats tool, with minimap2’s mapping locations as the ground truth; higher is better. The F-1 score is a common way of combining precision and

Figure 5: Accuracy-Latency-Throughput-Memory Footprint Tradeoffs of Rawalign vs. Baselines.

recall into a single metric, which we report individually in [Sup.Tab. S1](#).

3.1.3. Datasets. We use the same datasets as RawHash’s evaluation, labeled as d1 through d5, which include a range of organisms from viruses to humans. Specifically, d1 is SARS-CoV-2, d2 is *E. coli*, d3 is Yeast, d4 is Green Algae, and d5 is Human. We updated the Green Algae dataset (d4) to use all of the available 1.3 Gbp of ERR3237140, whereas RawHash used only 0.6 Gbp of this dataset. [Tab. 1](#) provides detailed information on each dataset.

3.1.4. System Specifications. With two exceptions, we run all CPU evaluations 64 threads on a dual-socket Intel Xeon Gold 6226R (2×16 physical cores, 2×32 logical cores) at 2.9GHz with 256GB of DDR4 RAM. Sigmap runs out of memory on the Intel system for the Human and Relative Abundance datasets; hence, we run Sigmap with these datasets using 64 threads on a dual-socket AMD EPYC 7742 (2×64 physical cores, 2×128 logical cores) at 2.25GHz with 1024GB of DDR4 RAM.

3.1.5. Parameter Settings. We empirically select all parameters used in RawAlign to optimize performance and accuracy. Specifically, for the *match bonus* B_{Match} and the *score threshold* $Score_{Threshold}$ (discussed in [§2.3](#)), we set the default values to $B_{Match} = 0.4$ and $Score_{Threshold} = 20$. These values were determined through a two-dimensional parameter sweep on the d2

E. coli dataset to achieve the best overall accuracy. To provide insights about the effect of the band width on the accuracy, we provide our parameter sweep evaluation in [§3.4](#).

3.2. Read Mapping

We run a read mapping experiment for all tools and datasets. [Tab. 2](#) shows the raw numeric results for five key metrics: memory footprint, throughput, analysis latency, sequencing latency, and accuracy, with the best tool in each dataset and metric highlighted in bold. [Fig. 5](#) shows the same results as a spider chart for each dataset, with each metric in a dataset normalized from worst (center, e.g., lowest throughput) to best (outside, e.g., highest throughput). Thus, a tool with a large area in the spider chart indicates a good overall tradeoff in all metrics, while a small area indicates a bad overall tradeoff between the metrics. We omit the RawHash2 and RawAlign-RH2 results from [Fig. 5](#) for readability.

We make seven key observations: First, RawAlign is consistently highly accurate for all datasets, and it is the only tool that is highly accurate for large reference databases (e.g., Human, Relative Abundance). Second, RawAlign has a low analysis latency (i.e., time taken for computation) and sequencing latency (i.e., time taken for sequencing). Third, RawAlign has a large area in [Fig. 5](#) for all datasets, i.e., RawAlign generalizes well to all evaluated datasets. Fourth, RawAlign’s memory footprint

Table 1: Dataset Details.

Organism	Flow Cell Version	Reads (#)	Bases (#)	SRA Accession	Reference Genome	Genome Size	
Read Mapping							
d1	<i>SARS-CoV-2</i>	R9.4	1,382,016	594M	CADDE Centre	GCF_009858895.2	29,903
d2	<i>E. coli</i>	R9.4	353,317	2,364M	ERR9127551	GCA_000007445.1	5M
d3	<i>Yeast</i>	R9.4	49,992	380M	SRR8648503	GCA_000146045.2	12M
d4	<i>Green Algae</i>	R9.4	63,215	1,335M	ERR3237140	GCF_000002595.2	111M
d5	<i>Human HG001</i>	R9.4	269,507	1,584M	FAB42260 Nanopore WGS	T2T-CHM13 (v2)	3,117M
Relative Abundance Estimation							
D1-D5		2,118,047	6,257M	d1-d5	d1-d5	3,246M	
Contamination Analysis							
D1 and D5		1,651,523	2,178M	d1 and d5	d1	29,903	

Dataset numbers (e.g., d1-d5) show the combined datasets.

Datasets are from R9.4. Base counts in millions (M).

depends mainly on the reference database size, requiring up to 83GB for the largest reference database (relative abundance), a size typically available in moderately sized servers. For the evaluated datasets with relatively small reference databases (d1-d4, Contamination), the memory footprint is at most 12.2GB, a size typically available in modern desktop computers and some laptops. Fifth, RawAlign’s mean throughput per thread is at least that of recent ONT nanopores (450 bp/s), *i.e.*, a single thread can analyze the signals generated by a nanopore in real-time. Sixth, for some datasets, RawAlign has higher throughput than RawHash, despite having more computational steps. The reason is that RawAlign’s higher accuracy enables higher confidence and hence quicker decisions to stop sequencing individual reads than in RawHash, leading to overall less data being analyzed. Seventh, RawAlign generalizes well to other seeding and filtering mechanisms, such as RawHash2, improving accuracy while maintaining high throughput without fine-tuning. RawAlign achieves even higher accuracy than RawAlign-RH2, demonstrating that fine-tuning the specific combination of seeding, filtering, and alignment steps can further improve accuracy.

We conclude that RawAlign is the only tool to generalize well across a wide range of reference database sizes and read set compositions. It is consistently highly accurate, has low latency, meets the real-time analysis throughput requirement of 450bp/s, and fits in the memory of typical laptop, desktop, or moderately sized server

systems, depending on the reference database size.

3.3. Relative Abundance

The relative abundance read set is artificially composed of the read sets from d1-d5; hence, the ground truth is known. We map the read set against the concatenation of the reference genomes d1-d5 and calculate relative abundance estimates based on the number of reads per organism reported by each tool. We consider minimap2 with basecalled reads as input as an additional baseline. We use the Euclidean distance to the ground truth relative abundance as the main accuracy metric. [Tab. 3](#) shows the results. We report the relative abundance results based on the number of bases instead of the number of reads in [Sup.§C](#).

We make three key observations. First, RawAlign is the most accurate among the raw signal analysis tools with a Euclidean distance of 0.12 to the ground truth and close to minimap2’s accuracy with a Euclidean distance of 0.05 to the ground truth. Second, RawAlign is the most accurate among the raw signal analysis tools for all organisms and is within 0.07 of the Euclidean distance of minimap2. Note that minimap2 has the advantage of having full-length basecalled reads as input, while RawAlign uses only a short prefix of each read for mapping. Third, we observe that RawAlign is much more accurate than RawAlign-RH2. The reason is that RawAlign-RH2 drops some correct candidates during the earlier aggressive *frequency filtering* of seeds [9], where high-frequency

Table 2: Numeric Results.

	Memory		Throughput (bp/s)	Analysis		Sequencing		Accuracy (F-1)
	Footprint (GB)			Latency (ms)		Latency (Chunks)		
d1 SARS-CoV-2								
UNCALLED	0.28		6,575	29.24		0.410	0.972	
Sigmap	28.25		350,565	1.11		1.005	0.711	
RawHash	4.21		502,043	0.94		1.238	0.925	
RawAlign	4.52		438,090	1.07		1.126	0.939	
RawHash2	4.32		670,152	0.71		1.219	0.935	
RawAlign-RH2	4.31		641,164	0.74		1.266	0.917	
d2 E. Coli								
UNCALLED	0.80		5,174	115.79		1.290	0.973	
Sigmap	111.17		19,216	34.44		2.111	0.967	
RawHash	4.27		49,560	19.75		3.200	0.928	
RawAlign	4.31		54,263	13.11		1.995	0.968	
RawHash2	4.46		128,692	7.51		3.270	0.934	
RawAlign-RH2	4.45		132,710	6.35		2.773	0.943	
d3 Yeast								
UNCALLED	0.58		5,152	159.30		2.773	0.941	
Sigmap	14.71		15,217	67.60		4.139	0.947	
RawHash	4.53		17,997	77.59		5.826	0.906	
RawAlign	4.53		17,855	48.39		3.071	0.963	
RawHash2	4.83		51,912	24.95		4.263	0.921	
RawAlign-RH2	4.89		55,515	18.63		3.321	0.944	
d4 Green Algae								
UNCALLED	1.26		8,174	440.81		11.790	0.840	
Sigmap	53.71		2,251	608.90		5.804	0.938	
RawHash	14.06		5,430	700.30		10.646	0.824	
RawAlign	12.20		5,871	276.09		4.514	0.932	
RawHash2	8.77		6,176	269.97		5.025	0.904	
RawAlign-RH2	9.45		6,897	210.83		4.064	0.910	
d5 Human								
UNCALLED	13.17		5,613	1,077.54		12.959	0.320	
Sigmap	313.40		195	16,296.43		10.401	0.327	
RawHash	56.94		1,299	6,318.98		10.695	0.557	
RawAlign	80.35		886	3,721.86		6.321	0.702	
RawHash2	96.39		540	6,357.51		7.794	0.585	
RawAlign-RH2	119.29		391	6,133.61		7.126	0.642	
Contamination								
UNCALLED	1.06		6,608	199.28		3.557	0.964	
Sigmap	111.65		405,956	1.21		2.062	0.650	
RawHash	4.28		524,043	1.14		2.409	0.872	
RawAlign	4.50		455,376	2.00		3.227	0.938	
RawHash2	4.26		644,209	0.87		1.659	0.885	
RawAlign-RH2	4.24		655,537	1.15		1.796	0.917	
Relative Abundance								
UNCALLED	10.87		6,722	309.08		4.921	0.218	
Sigmap	506.34		182	5,670.36		3.338	0.406	
RawHash	60.76		597	2,264.01		3.816	0.459	
RawAlign	83.76		480	1,652.16		2.336	0.754	
RawHash2	97.56		562	2,122.52		3.404	0.363	
RawAlign-RH2	119.02		576	1,885.22		3.131	0.418	

seeds that occur too often in the reference are discarded to reduce computational load. However, this can eliminate valid matches, which cannot be recovered by the later alignment step, potentially leading to biased relative abundance estimates. In contrast, RawAlign does not apply frequency filtering, resulting in high accuracy at the cost of some performance (see Tab. 2).

We draw two key takeaways. First, RawAlign can be directly used to estimate relative abundances as an end-to-end use case with high accuracy and without the need for basecalling. Second, early aggressive filters can limit the benefits of alignment. Fine-tuning filters leads to better accuracy/performance tradeoffs.

3.4. Band Width Parameter Sweep

To minimize the computational overhead of alignment, we use banded dynamic time warping (see §2.4.3). If the width of the band is chosen too narrow, accuracy will be degraded. If it is too wide, performance will suffer.

Table 3: Read Ratio Relative Abundances.

Tool	SARS-CoV-2	E. coli	Yeast	Green Algae	Human	Distance
Ground Truth	0.652	0.167	0.024	0.030	0.127	-
minimap2	0.613	0.163	0.025	0.053	0.147	0.050
UNCALLED	0.072	0.466	0.001	0.150	0.312	0.689
Sigmap	0.201	0.446	0.002	0.123	0.229	0.549
RawHash	0.309	0.440	0.000	0.073	0.178	0.445
RawAlign	0.565	0.248	0.002	0.050	0.136	0.123
RawHash2	0.130	0.537	0.000	0.123	0.210	0.653
RawAlign-RH2	0.208	0.491	0.000	0.099	0.203	0.560

We parameter sweep the band width as a fraction of the length of the read fragment to be aligned on the d2 *E. Coli* dataset, and plot accuracy and throughput. Fig. 6 shows the results.

We observe that a band width of 20% of the length of the read fragment is sufficient to achieve the best accuracy (in terms of F-1 score), while simultaneously maximizing throughput. The reason that throughput is also maximized is that the pathological behavior of a too-narrow band width causes low confidence mapping candidates, meaning reads have to be analyzed for longer to reach a decision.

Based on this parameter sweep, we choose 20% as the default band width for RawAlign.

Figure 6: Band Width Parameter Sweep on d2 *E. coli*.

3.5. DTW Performance Optimizations

Figure 7: Throughput with each Additional DTW Performance Optimization on d3 Yeast.

To understand the impact of each performance optimization proposed in §2.4, we run a read mapping experiment on the d3 Yeast dataset. The experiment starts with

a *naive DTW implementation*, an unoptimized version of DTW that computes the full dynamic programming matrix without any performance enhancements. In each subsequent run, we iteratively enable a new optimization on top of the previous ones. Fig. 7 shows the results.

We make three key observations. First, we observe that anchor-guided alignments, banded alignments, and SIMD each significantly increase throughput. Second, we observe that the early termination strategy yields only a small benefit on the d3 Yeast dataset. This is mainly due to the relatively small reference genome size, which results in a small number of candidate regions per read. In contrast, the early termination strategy is most powerful when it can quickly eliminate many poor candidates of a read after a first good candidate is found. Thus, the early termination strategy is strongest for large reference databases. Third, we observe that in the case of the d3 Yeast dataset, even a naive DTW implementation has a reasonably high throughput. This is because although the naive DTW subroutine is inefficient, it is called infrequently due to the small number of candidate regions per read. This is not the case for large reference databases.

We conclude that (1) the performance optimizations presented in §2.4 are effective, and (2) their relative importance depends on the size of the reference database.

4. Related Work

Several studies have explored real-time genome analysis of raw nanopore signals by leveraging adaptive sampling techniques [6–9, 11–18, 20, 21, 34]. Methods such as SquiggleNet [18], DeepSelectNet [20], and RawMap [21] employ machine learning techniques to classify raw nanopore signals to specific species without performing read mapping. Sigmoni [34] adopts a strategy similar to that of SPUMONI [35] and SPUMONI 2 [36], facilitating classification without basecalling.

UNCALLED [13], Sigmap [12], RawHash [8], and RawHash2 [9] are particularly relevant to our work, as they map raw nanopore signals to a reference genome without relying on computationally intensive basecalling steps.

UNCALLED [13] maps raw signals to a reference genome by computing the probabilities of k-mers that each raw signal segment (*i.e.*, event) may represent, using a k-mer model that provides expected event values for all possible k-mers. It then identifies sequences of matching k-mers between the most probable k-mers of events and the reference genome using an FM-index [37]. However, as the genome size increases, this probabilistic model

faces challenges in accurately identifying matching regions due to the vast number of potential matches [13]. While UNCALLED maintains high accuracy for small genomes (*e.g.*, *E. coli* and *Yeast*), its accuracy significantly declines when applied to larger genomes, such as the human genome.

Sigmap [12] addresses mapping to larger genomes by computing the Euclidean distance between raw signals and a reference genome, after converting the reference genome into its expected signal representation using k-mer models. This distance calculation allows for identifying segments of raw signals that closely match particular regions in the reference genome. However, calculating the Euclidean distance between high-dimensional vectors is computationally expensive and suffers from the *curse of dimensionality* [38], limiting its scalability and efficiency for large genomes.

RawHash [8] maps raw nanopore signals to a reference genome using a quick hash-based search followed by chaining. To do so, RawHash quantized (*i.e.*, bucketing) noisy raw signals such that the signals from the same DNA content are assigned to the same hash value even though their corresponding raw signals may be slightly different than each other. This coarse-grained hash-based sequence comparison is fast and scales well to large reference genomes but has relatively low accuracy. RawHash2 [9] provides a more sensitive quantization mechanism and mapping strategies. In doing so, RawHash2 provides improvements in terms of speedup and accuracy compared to RawHash. However, RawHash and RawHash2 still lack fine-grained sequence alignments in the output, limiting their applicability to downstream analysis tasks (*e.g.*, variant calling).

Although earlier works [7, 14, 16, 39] have explored performing alignment on raw nanopore signals using DTW [22–24], these works lack an accurate and fast seeding mechanism. Without such a seeding mechanism, costly alignment operations must be performed for every position in the reference genome. This approach is impractical as it cannot scale to larger genomes, especially when performing real-time analysis. RawAlign is the first work to integrate a fast and accurate hash-based seeding mechanism [8, 9] before performing the alignment. By doing so, RawAlign makes it practical to perform alignment on larger genomes.

5. Discussion

RawAlign’s Seed-Filter-Align approach is inspired by conventional basecalled read mappers. We have com-

pared RawAlign to the highly engineered state-of-the-art basecalled read mapper minimap2 in the relative abundance use case and observe that RawAlign is approaching the accuracy of minimap2. In the future, developing downstream analysis tools that operate directly on raw nanopore signals may enable more insightful and direct comparisons between analyses conducted on basecalled sequences and those performed on raw signal data. Such tools could reveal nuances and variations in the data often lost during the basecalling process, potentially leading to an improved understanding of genomic variations and more accurate genomic analyses. To achieve this, we identify two key limitations that can be tackled in future work to improve the accuracy and performance of raw signal analysis.

First, RawAlign cannot perform alignment between a pair of raw signals where none of the pairs are from a reference genome. This is mainly due to the seeding step RawAlign builds on and RawAlign’s requirement to perform segmentation before performing the alignment (*i.e.*, the alignment is performed between events). Performing a pairwise alignment between raw nanopore signals can enable identifying overlaps between signals and subsequently constructing *de novo* assemblies from these overlaps as miniasm does [33].

Second, the specific alignment operations (*i.e.*, edit operations such as insertions, deletions, and substitutions) between a raw nanopore signal and a reference genome can be identified by performing *backtracking* after constructing the DTW dynamic programming table. Backtracking involves tracing the optimal path through the dynamic programming matrix from the endpoint back to the start, allowing us to reconstruct the sequence of edits that constitute the optimal alignment. Generating these edit operations in a mapping file can be useful to enable subsequent steps in genome analysis, such as variant calling. However, backtracking significantly increases computational overhead because it requires additional memory and processing time to trace the optimal alignment path through the DTW matrix. To enable RawAlign to scale to much larger genomes while generating edit operations in real-time, further algorithmic optimizations are needed. These may include more efficient data structures for storing the dynamic programming matrix, heuristic methods to approximate the alignment path, or parallelization techniques to accelerate backtracking.

We find that Seed-Filter-Align is already an effective paradigm for raw signal mapping as implemented in RawAlign, and in the future, may directly compete with

basecalled read mappers once it is engineered to a similar extent as existing basecalled read mappers.

6. Conclusion

We present RawAlign, a tool that improves the state-of-the-art in raw nanopore signal mapping by integrating fast and scalable hash-based seeding with highly accurate alignment using dynamic time warping (DTW). We address key challenges in combining DTW with hash-based mapping, including computational cost and integration into the mapping decision process, by proposing optimizations such as chaining-based filtering, early termination, anchor-guided alignment, and SIMD vectorization.

To our knowledge, RawAlign is the first work to combine raw signal seeding and alignment via dynamic time warping. We have extensively compared RawAlign to UNCALLED [13], Sigmap [12], RawHash [8], and RawHash2 [9]. In our comparison, we have demonstrated the benefits of RawAlign’s Seed-Filter-Align approach over prior methods for raw signal mapping.

Our comprehensive evaluations demonstrate that RawAlign consistently achieves high accuracy and low latency across a wide range of reference genome sizes, including large genomes like the human genome. RawAlign meets the real-time analysis throughput requirements and generalizes well to different datasets. We conclude that RawAlign is the first tool to enable accurate, fast, and scalable mapping of raw nanopore signals to large genomes without basecalling, making it practical for real-time analysis and downstream tasks such as variant calling.

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References

- [1] W. R. McCombie *et al.*, “Next-generation sequencing technologies,” *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 2019.
- [2] Y. Wang *et al.*, “Nanopore sequencing technology, bioinformatics and applications,” *Nature Biotechnology*, 2021.
- [3] G. A. Logsdon *et al.*, “Long-read human genome sequencing and its applications,” *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 2020.

- [4] A. M. Giani *et al.*, “Long walk to genomics: History and current approaches to genome sequencing and assembly,” *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal*, 2020.
- [5] Oxford Nanopore Technologies, “MinION,” <https://nanoporetech.com/products/minion>, 2023, accessed: September 23, 2024.
- [6] M. Loose *et al.*, “Real-Time Selective Sequencing Using Nanopore Technology,” *Nature Methods*, 2016.
- [7] T. Dunn *et al.*, “SquiggleFilter: An Accelerator for Portable Virus Detection,” *MICRO*, 2021.
- [8] C. Firtina *et al.*, “RawHash: enabling fast and accurate real-time analysis of raw nanopore signals for large genomes,” *Bioinformatics*, 2023.
- [9] C. Firtina *et al.*, “RawHash2: Mapping Raw Nanopore Signals Using Hash-Based Seeding and Adaptive Quantization,” *Bioinformatics*, 2024.
- [10] O. Mutlu and C. Firtina, “Accelerating Genome Analysis via Algorithm-Architecture Co-Design,” *DAC*, 2023.
- [11] Sam Kovaka *et al.*, “Uncalled4 improves nanopore DNA and RNA modification detection via fast and accurate signal alignment,” *bioRxiv*, 2024, accessed: September 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2F2024.03.05.583511>
- [12] H. Zhang *et al.*, “Real-time mapping of nanopore raw signals,” *Bioinformatics*, 2021.
- [13] S. Kovaka *et al.*, “Targeted nanopore sequencing by real-time mapping of raw electrical signal with UNCALLED,” *Nature Biotechnology*, 2021.
- [14] P. J. Shih *et al.*, “Efficient Real-Time Selective Genome Sequencing on Resource-Constrained Devices,” *GigaScience*, 2023.
- [15] H. Sadasivan *et al.*, “Accelerated Dynamic Time Warping on GPU for Selective Nanopore Sequencing,” *Journal of Biotechnology and Biomedicine*, 2024.
- [16] H. Gamaarachchi *et al.*, “GPU Accelerated Adaptive Banded Event Alignment for Rapid Comparative Nanopore Signal Analysis,” *BMC Bioinformatics*, vol. 21, 2020.
- [17] S. Samarasinghe *et al.*, “Energy Efficient Adaptive Banded Event Alignment using OpenCL on FPGAs,” in *ICIAFS*, 2021.
- [18] Y. Bao *et al.*, “SquiggleNet: real-time, direct classification of nanopore signals,” *Genome Biology*, 2021.
- [19] B. Noordijk *et al.*, “baseLess: Lightweight Detection of Sequences in Raw MinION Data,” *Bioinformatics Advances*, 2023.
- [20] A. Senanayake *et al.*, “DeepSelectNet: Deep Neural Network Based Selective Sequencing for Oxford Nanopore Sequencing,” *BMC Bioinformatics*, 2023.
- [21] H. Sadasivan *et al.*, “Rapid Real-time Squiggle Classification for Read Until Using RawMap,” *Arch. Clin. Biomed. Res.*, 2023.
- [22] V. Velichko and N. Zagoruyko, “Automatic Recognition of 200 Words,” *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies*, 1970.
- [23] H. Sakoe and S. Chiba, “A Similarity Evaluation of Speech Patterns by Dynamic Programming,” in *Nat. Meeting of Institute of Electronic Communications Engineers of Japan*, 1970.
- [24] H. Sakoe and S. Chiba, “Dynamic-Programming Approach to Continuous Speech Recognition,” in *Proc. International Congress of Acoustics, Budapest, 1971*.
- [25] M. Flynn, “Very high-speed computing systems,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 54, no. 12, pp. 1901–1909, 1966.
- [26] H. Li, “Minimap2: Pairwise Alignment for Nucleotide Sequences,” *Bioinformatics*, 2018.
- [27] H. Li, “Aligning sequence reads, clone sequences and assembly contigs with bwa-mem,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1303.3997*, 2013, accessed: September 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1303.3997>
- [28] M. Vasimuddin *et al.*, “Efficient architecture-aware acceleration of bwa-mem for multicore systems,” in *IPDPS*, 2019.
- [29] S. B. Needleman and C. D. Wunsch, “A general method applicable to the search for similarities in the amino acid sequence of two proteins,” *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 1970.
- [30] M. Susic and M. Sikic, “Edlib: a c/c++ library for fast, exact sequence alignment using edit distance,” *Bioinformatics*, 2017.
- [31] H. Suzuki and M. Kasahara, “Introducing Difference Recurrence Relations for Faster Semi-Global Alignment of Long Sequences,” *BMC Bioinformatics*, 2018.
- [32] Z. Xia *et al.*, “A review of parallel implementations for the smith–waterman algorithm,” *Interdisciplinary Sciences: Computational Life Sciences*, 2022.
- [33] H. Li, “Minimap and miniasm: fast mapping and de novo assembly for noisy long sequences,” *Bioinformatics*, 2016.
- [34] V. S. Shivakumar *et al.*, “Sigmoni: classification of nanopore signal with a compressed pangenome index,” *Bioinform.*, 2024.
- [35] O. Ahmed *et al.*, “Pan-genomic matching statistics for targeted nanopore sequencing,” *iScience*, vol. 24, no. 6, Jun. 2021.
- [36] O. Y. Ahmed *et al.*, “SPUMONI 2: improved classification using a pangenome index of minimizer digests,” *Genome Biology*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 122, May 2023.
- [37] P. Ferragina and G. Manzini, “Opportunistic data structures with applications,” in *FOCS*, 2000.
- [38] R. Bellman, “Dynamic Programming,” *Science*, vol. 153, no. 3731, pp. 34–37, Jul. 1966.
- [39] H. Sadasivan *et al.*, “Accelerating Minimap2 for Accurate Long Read Alignment on GPUs,” *Journal of Biotechnology and Biomedicine*, 2023.

Supplementary Material for RawAlign: Accurate, Fast, and Scalable Raw Nanopore Signal Mapping via Combining Seeding and Alignment

A. Background

A.1. Offline Reference Database Pre-Processing

A *reference database* is a set of a priori known biological sequences that reads should be compared to during mapping. For example, the reference database could consist of a chromosome, a set of genes, a genome, or multiple genomes. Reference databases are often available and accepted by read mappers in FASTA file format, *i.e.*, as a set of basecalled nucleotide sequences. RawAlign pre-processes the reference database in two steps: First, basecalled nucleotide reference sequences are converted into a form that is easier to compare with a raw signal read (Sup.§A.1.1). Second, the reference sequences are *indexed* into a hash table that allows querying for small exact matches during mapping (Sup.§A.1.2).

A.1.1. Expected Event Generation. To ease comparison with a raw signal read, RawAlign converts the basecalled reference database into sequences of raw signals that would be observed in a perfect noise-free sequencer, called *expected event sequences*. RawAlign obtains expected event sequences in an offline pre-processing step based on a model of the nanopore provided by the manufacturer, like in prior works (*e.g.*, [1, 2]).

A.1.2. Indexing. Mapping with the Seed-Filter-Align paradigm requires an *index*, a data structure that can be efficiently queried for locations of small exact matches between the read and the reference. To this end, RawAlign cuts the expected event sequences into short snippets and quantizes them into *seeds*. The seeds are inserted into a hash table, where each seed is a key, and the value is a list of locations where that seed occurs in the reference database. RawAlign leverages the pre-processing steps from RawHash [1].

A.2. Online Read Pre-Processing

Current nanopore sequencers take multiple measurements as each nucleotide base passes through the nanopore, leading to many largely redundant measurements. To simplify the further computation, RawAlign converts them into *event sequences*, where redundant measurements are averaged into a single value. This conversion is called *segmentation*. It is not trivial since the translocation rate of the sequence molecule through the nanopore is variable, *i.e.*, it is not obvious which groups of signals should be averaged together. RawAlign leverages the segmentation logic proposed in Scrapie [3] and used by UNCALLED [4], Sigmap [2], and RawHash [1].

B. Full Results

[Sup.Tab. S1](#) reports the full results of the read mapping evaluation in §3.2 with the best tool in each dataset and metric highlighted in bold. The metrics are defined as follows:

- **Indexing memory footprint** (GB) during indexing as reported by Ubuntu's `time` package; lower is better.
- **Mapping memory footprint** (GB) during mapping as reported by Ubuntu's `time` package; lower is better.
- **Mean throughput** (bp/s) per thread of mapping as reported by each tool in its PAF output. The throughput should match at least the throughput of a nanopore (*e.g.*, 450 bp/s in recent ONT sequencers); higher is better.
- **Median throughput** (bp/s) per thread of mapping as reported by each tool in its PAF output. The throughput should match at least the throughput of a nanopore (*e.g.*, 450 bp/s in recent ONT sequencers); higher is better.
- Mean **analysis latency** (ms), *i.e.*, the time spent computing for mapping reads as reported by each tool in its PAF output; lower is better. We also report the median analysis latency in [Sup.Tab. S1](#).
- Mean **sequencing latency** (bases), *i.e.*, the number of bases needed to reach a mapping decision for each read, as reported by each tool in its PAF output; lower is better.
- Mean **sequencing latency** (chunks), *i.e.*, the number of 450 basepair-sized chunks needed to reach a mapping decision for each read, as reported by each tool in its PAF output; lower is better. Uncalled reports a number of bases instead of a number of chunks, which we convert to a number of chunks by dividing by 450.
- **Precision** based on the annotations from Uncalled's `pafstats` tool, with `minimap2`'s mapping locations as the ground truth; higher is better.
- **Recall** based on the annotations from Uncalled's `pafstats` tool, with `minimap2`'s mapping locations as the ground truth; higher is better.
- **F-1 score** based on the annotations from Uncalled's `pafstats` tool, with `minimap2`'s mapping locations as the ground truth; higher is better. The F-1 score is a combination of precision and recall.

Table S1: Numeric Results.

d1 SARS-CoV-2	Indexing Memory		Mapping Memory		Mean Throughput		Median Throughput		Analysis		Mean Sequencing		Sequencing	
	Footprint (GB)	Footprint (GB)	Footprint (GB)	Footprint (GB)	(bp/s)	(bp/s)	(bp/s)	(bp/s)	Latency (ms)	Latency (Bases)	Latency (Chunks)	Precision	Recall	F-1
UNCALLED	0.07	0.28	6,575	6,433	29.24	185	0.410	0.955	0.991	0.972				
Sigmap	0.01	28.25	350,565	355,001	1.11	-	1.005	0.993	0.554	0.711				
RawHash	0.01	4.21	502,043	454,272	0.94	514	1.238	0.983	0.874	0.925				
RawAlign	0.01	4.52	438,090	425,341	1.07	-	1.126	1.000	0.885	0.939				
RawHash2	0.01	4.32	670,152	662,431	0.71	498	1.219	0.977	0.896	0.935				
RawAlign-RH2	0.01	4.31	641,164	639,757	0.74	522	1.266	1.000	0.846	0.917				
d2 E. Coli														
UNCALLED	0.12	0.80	5,174	5,115	115.79	580	1.290	0.982	0.965	0.973				
Sigmap	0.40	111.17	19,216	18,063	34.44	-	2.111	0.984	0.950	0.967				
RawHash	0.35	4.27	49,560	44,379	19.75	1,376	3.200	0.956	0.901	0.928				
RawAlign	0.39	4.31	54,263	48,778	13.11	-	1.995	0.987	0.950	0.968				
RawHash2	0.35	4.46	128,692	124,544	7.51	1,380	3.270	0.986	0.887	0.934				
RawAlign-RH2	0.39	4.45	132,710	129,523	6.35	1,163	2.773	0.989	0.901	0.943				
d3 Yeast														
UNCALLED	0.30	0.58	5,152	4,671	159.30	1,248	2.773	0.944	0.937	0.941				
Sigmap	1.04	14.71	15,217	14,524	67.60	-	4.139	0.986	0.911	0.947				
RawHash	0.76	4.53	17,997	16,853	77.59	2,566	5.826	0.985	0.839	0.906				
RawAlign	0.86	4.53	17,855	16,369	48.39	-	3.071	0.962	0.964	0.963				
RawHash2	0.76	4.83	51,912	50,323	24.95	1,825	4.263	0.963	0.882	0.921				
RawAlign-RH2	0.86	4.89	55,515	53,853	18.63	1,408	3.321	0.958	0.930	0.944				
d4 Green Algae														
UNCALLED	11.96	1.26	8,174	8,132	440.81	5,306	11.790	0.888	0.798	0.840				
Sigmap	8.63	53.71	2,251	2,150	608.90	-	5.804	0.974	0.905	0.938				
RawHash	5.33	14.06	5,430	4,850	700.30	4,723	10.646	0.966	0.719	0.824				
RawAlign	6.16	12.20	5,871	5,238	276.09	-	4.514	0.913	0.953	0.932				
RawHash2	5.26	8.77	6,176	5,825	269.97	2,157	5.025	0.936	0.874	0.904				
RawAlign-RH2	6.09	9.45	6,897	6,623	210.83	1,734	4.064	0.925	0.896	0.910				
d5 Human														
UNCALLED	48.43	13.17	5,613	6,064	1,077.54	5,832	12.959	0.487	0.238	0.320				
Sigmap	227.77	313.40	195	129	16,296.43	-	10.401	0.429	0.264	0.327				
RawHash	83.09	56.94	1,299	269	6,318.98	4,773	10.695	0.894	0.405	0.557				
RawAlign	107.44	80.35	886	291	3,721.86	-	6.321	0.696	0.707	0.702				
RawHash2	83.06	96.39	540	302	6,357.51	3,441	7.794	0.877	0.439	0.585				
RawAlign-RH2	107.43	119.29	391	331	6,133.61	3,139	7.126	0.874	0.507	0.642				
Contamination														
UNCALLED	0.07	1.06	6,608	6,431	199.28	1,601	3.557	0.938	0.991	0.964				
Sigmap	0.01	111.65	405,956	364,466	1.21	-	2.062	0.786	0.554	0.650				
RawHash	0.01	4.28	524,043	461,281	1.14	1,039	2.409	0.870	0.874	0.872				
RawAlign	0.01	4.50	455,376	433,378	2.00	-	3.227	0.997	0.885	0.938				
RawHash2	0.01	4.26	644,209	638,549	0.87	682	1.659	0.873	0.896	0.885				
RawAlign-RH2	0.01	4.24	655,537	645,277	1.15	768	1.796	1.000	0.846	0.917				
Relative Abundance														
UNCALLED	47.79	10.87	6,722	7,233	309.08	2,215	4.921	0.763	0.127	0.218				
Sigmap	238.32	506.34	182	166	5,670.36	-	3.338	0.793	0.273	0.406				
RawHash	153.12	60.76	597	402	2,264.01	1,685	3.816	0.947	0.303	0.459				
RawAlign	163.90	83.76	480	339	1,652.16	-	2.336	0.946	0.627	0.754				
RawHash2	153.29	97.56	562	450	2,122.52	1,495	3.404	0.950	0.224	0.363				
RawAlign-RH2	163.89	119.02	576	521	1,885.22	1,371	3.131	0.961	0.267	0.418				

C. Bases Ratio Relative Abundances

We calculate relative abundance estimates based on the number of bases per organism reported by each tool. This metric corresponds to the evaluation in RawHash [1], but we believe the estimation based on the number of reads per organism is more representative in the context on ReadUntil. The read set is artificially composed of the read sets from d1-d5; hence, the ground truth is known. We consider minimap2 with basecalled reads as input as an additional baseline. We use the Euclidean distance to the ground truth relative abundance as the main accuracy metric. Sup.Tab. S2 shows the results. We report the relative abundance results based on the number of reads instead of the number of bases in §3.3.

We observe that RawAlign’s estimates are entirely inaccurate, even though it achieves a high F-1 score on the Relative Abundance dataset. The reason is that RawAlign stops sequencing each read after successfully mapping between 200-400 bases on average for all organisms (a desired property in the context of ReadUntil) thus it weights each read approximately equally. This is why the bases ratio-relative abundances reported by RawAlign are close to the read ratio-relative abundances reported in §3.3. In truth, the reads vary significantly in length, meaning RawAlign weighs them "wrongly", although it operates as desired in the context of ReadUntil. It is unclear why all raw signal baselines seemingly weigh reads correctly. Since all baselines have significantly worse F-1 scores on the Relative Abundance dataset, there is a possibility that this is down to good fortune. Note that minimap2 is run on the complete reads and not reads "cut short" due to ReadUntil, hence it can weigh the reads correctly.

We conclude that when estimating relative abundances using RawAlign, it is more representative to use the number of reads mapped instead of the number of bases mapped.

Table S2: Bases Ratio Relative Abundances.

Tool	SARS-CoV-2	E. Coli	Yeast	Green Algae	Human	Distance
Ground Truth	0.095	0.378	0.061	0.213	0.253	-
minimap2	0.081	0.383	0.061	0.227	0.248	0.021
UNCALLED	0.002	0.561	0.000	0.228	0.208	0.219
Sigmap	0.044	0.442	0.008	0.156	0.350	0.148
RawHash	0.129	0.486	0.001	0.129	0.254	0.153
RawAlign	0.501	0.255	0.003	0.064	0.176	0.460
RawHash2	0.036	0.512	0.001	0.154	0.298	0.175
RawAlign-RH2	0.074	0.512	0.000	0.125	0.288	0.177

D. Reproducing the Results

All results can easily be reproduced by following the steps in the README at <https://github.com/CMU-SAFARI/RawAlign/blob/ee59c4e5d04d8464e134fe5c0c9e1cd38ccc9cc3/test/README.md>.

In particular, all experimental results are reproduced in one go by the following commands:

```
#!/bin/bash
#number of threads
THR=64

cd read_mapping
cd d1_sars-cov-2_r94 && bash 0_run_all.sh $THR \
  && cd comparison && bash 0_run.sh && cd ../..
cd d2_ecoli_r94 && bash 0_run_all.sh $THR \
  && cd comparison && bash 0_run.sh && cd ../..
cd d3_yeast_r94 && bash 0_run_all.sh $THR \
  && cd comparison && bash 0_run.sh && cd ../..
cd d4_green_algae_r94 && bash 0_run_all.sh $THR \
  && cd comparison && bash 0_run.sh && cd ../..
cd d5_human_na12878_r94 && bash 0_run_all.sh $THR \
  && cd comparison && bash 0_run.sh && cd ../..
cd ..

cd relative_abundance && \
  bash 0_run_all.sh $THR && cd ..
cd contamination && \
  bash 0_run_all.sh $THR && cd ..
```

Supplementary References

- [1] C. Firtina *et al.*, "RawHash: enabling fast and accurate real-time analysis of raw nanopore signals for large genomes," *Bioinformatics*, 2023.
- [2] H. Zhang *et al.*, "Real-time mapping of nanopore raw signals," *Bioinformatics*, 2021.
- [3] Oxford Nanopore Technologies, "Scrappie, <https://github.com/nanoporetech/scrappie>," 2019, accessed: September 23, 2024.
- [4] S. Kovaka *et al.*, "Targeted nanopore sequencing by real-time mapping of raw electrical signal with UNCALLED," *Nature Biotechnology*, 2021.